

Research Software Alliance

Strategic Plan 2025–2028

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Join Us! Drive the future of research software

Research software is at a critical inflection point. **With additional resources, ReSA can scale impact, drive innovation, and ensure that research software is supported in its critical role to solidify next-generation research and innovation, and economic growth.**

Securing the needed resources is a primary goal of ReSA’s operations in 2025–28. We are actively seeking partners to join our dynamic group of organisations coordinating across global communities to accelerate research. For partnership and funding opportunities, please contact michelle@researchsoft.org.

Executive Summary: Advancing the global research software community

The [Research Software Alliance \(ReSA\)](#) is a global organisation that aims to unite decision-makers and key influencers across the international research and innovation community.

ReSA fills a crucial niche, creating much-needed opportunities for stakeholders across the entire research software community to come together to discover solutions, learn best practices, and share the knowledge that advances progress. Through active community engagement, and inclusive and transparent practices, ReSA advances the agency and recognition of research software and research software professionals. **ReSA's key achievements include:**

Global Policy

ReSA co-authored position papers such as the [critical role of research software in AI-driven research](#), to inform global and national strategies.

Community-Led Standards

ReSA co-led creation of the [FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\) Principles](#), which engaged **500+ stakeholders globally** and has [increasing adoption](#).

Funding Mobilisation

ReSA engaged **60+ funding organisations** through the [Research Software Funders Forum](#), leading to initiatives such as the [Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability](#) (ADORE.software), which has major funders as signatories.

Strengthening Careers

ReSA provides secretariat support for the [International Council of Research Software Engineers \(RSE\) Associations](#) to continue to advance **RSE as a recognised career path**. The Council is predicted to grow to at least 50 countries globally.

Collaboration

ReSA co-chairs the [Research Software Infrastructure Forum](#), where **20 member organisations** drive alignment across infrastructures that serve the research community, such as use cases focused on tracking research software impact.

How ReSA works: Exchange, engage, and evolve

Research software is increasingly recognised as critical to research outcomes. Yet research software, and the people who develop and maintain it, operate with tremendously unstable resources and funding. This instability negatively impacts innovation by slowing research and creating unstable career pathways.

There is an urgent need for international cooperation that supports research software to solidify next-generation research and innovation, and economic growth.

ReSA's mission is centered around community empowerment – bringing decision makers and key influencers together to advance research software and the research software community. The outcomes that ReSA works to achieve are developed in close partnership with our community. ReSA's theory of change describes how ReSA's activities both have and continue to achieve outcomes and impacts. It is anchored in three pillars: **exchange, engage, and evolve**.

ReSA's focus for 2025 & beyond: People, policy, and infrastructure

As highlighted, the outcomes that ReSA aims to achieve have been developed in close partnership with our community. Over the next three years, our community will continue to focus efforts around driving significant improvements in three key areas: **people, policy, and infrastructure.**

People

- Bolstering of social infrastructures that support communities such as national and regional RSE associations, and thematic communities (e.g., training)
- Recognition and reward of research software work by research performing organisations, and national research assessment activities.
- Increased belonging and representation in the research software community.

Policy

- Implementation support for open software within open science policies.
- Alignment of policies by stakeholders such as publishers (to support software citation), funders (to support FAIRness) and employers (to support career paths).
- Ensure stakeholder funding increasingly supports research software and its personnel, and is provided by a range of stakeholders at different levels.

Infrastructure

- Maturation of tools that measure software, its community, and its impact, enabling rewards and recognition, and that assess compliance with standards and guidelines, such that they meet the needs of a range of stakeholders and are easily accessible.
- Identification of needed infrastructure, including software repositories and registries, to enable support that provides sustainability.
- Development and implementation of community-agreed standards.

1. Introduction

The Research Software Alliance (ReSA) is an international non-profit organisation with the following vision and mission:

Vision: Research software and those who develop and maintain it are recognised and valued as fundamental and vital to research worldwide.

Mission: To advance the research software ecosystem by collaborating with decision makers and key influencers.

ReSA’s mission is woven around **community empowerment** – bringing **leaders and key influencers** together to advance research software and the research software community. The outcomes that ReSA works to achieve are developed in close partnership with our community. ReSA’s theory of change describes how ReSA’s activities both have and continue to achieve outcomes and impacts. It is anchored in three pillars: **exchange, engage and evolve**.

This strategic plan builds upon the [previous strategic plan](#) to outline how ReSA facilitates achievement of these to improve research outcomes.

2. Landscape analysis

It is useful to understand the research software community that ReSA's mission seeks to improve collaboration across, including its challenges and evolution.

2.1 The international research software community

ReSA engages multiple [stakeholder groups](#) across the international research software community to collaborate to achieve common goals. ReSA's community encompasses many relevant research software organisations, initiatives, and communities that have a national or regional focus, disciplinary focus, or thematic focus (such as software citation or representation of research software engineer (RSEs)). These include research in academic, research laboratory, industry and government settings.

In addition to those that focus directly on research software, there is a broader community of others for whom software is just a small part of their interest; these are also relevant stakeholders. Some examples are communities that focus on open science, reproducibility, roles and careers for people who are less visible in research, publishing and review, and other types of scholarly products and digital objects. The breadth of the research software community is depicted in the following figure:

Consequently, it is very hard to define the “research software community” in a clear-cut way, and ReSA is open to engaging with all organisations that identify themselves as part of this. There are many communities and organisations that support research software, and whilst some of these groups come together in different ways, there continues to be a need for a coordinating organisation such as ReSA. ReSA’s formation five years ago filled a critical need, functioning as a coordinating entity for the research software community, working with all of these stakeholders in a formal way (as the research data community does through the Research Data Alliance) to maximise collective impact.

2.2 Community challenges

The innovations of today and tomorrow rely on research software. Software for research and innovation is critical infrastructure for research, industry, and civil society partners. Research software is already recognised as critical to research outcome. Not only has research software expedited scientific progress, it is now a crucial tool for ensuring the reproducibility of research outcomes. ReSA’s [position paper](#) on the criticality of research software in artificial intelligence (AI)-driven research also emphasises the need to ensure that the focus on technological

infrastructure to support AI acceleration includes research software and its personnel as a vital part of that infrastructure.

Yet research software, and the people who develop and maintain it, operate with tremendously unstable resources and funding, or simply without payment as there is no other choice. Whilst [software in science is ubiquitous](#), it is typically not an area of focus or priority. This instability negatively impacts innovation by slowing research and creating unstable career pathways. There is an urgent need for international cooperation that supports research software to solidify next-generation research and innovation, and economic growth. Challenges that would benefit from resolution in the next few years include:

Within the research software community (to align and leverage the interests of varied stakeholders):

1. Limited coherence at the international level, as national approaches to recognising and valuing research software are commonly siloed from each other.
2. Differences in how research disciplines are evolving in their usage and valuing of research software and its personnel.
3. Scarcity of research software social infrastructure that utilises collective capacity to achieve common community goals to facilitate impactful, collaborative solutions that would otherwise not occur.
4. A deficit of international principles and standards needed to enable cohesion in research software.
5. Need for significant broadening of research software workforce to ensure more representation, participation and broader ideas.
6. Lack of engagement and incentives around research software in much of the Global South.

Within the broader research community (to normalise a research culture that supports and values research software):

1. Limited consideration of research software as a foundational part of open science, despite open software being one of the key elements (as defined by [UNESCO](#), alongside open research data, open hardware, scientific publications, and open educational resources).
2. Need for research software to be considered an equally valued product as research data, as discussed in initiatives such as Output Management Plan, citations, etc.
3. Lack of integration with open source scientific initiatives, limiting code sustainability and sharing of best practices with the open source software community.
4. Insufficient integration of research software areas such as reforming research assessment, research impact metrics, and metascience, resulting in under-emphasis of research software in these advancements.

2.3 The next phase of evolution

Whilst the research software community is a critical part of the research sector, existing challenges need support to be resolved, and new challenges will continue to appear as technology progresses and the research sector evolves. ReSA seeks to assist in ensuring significant improvements in key areas. To achieve this, ReSA encourages focus on three major areas: people, policy, and infrastructure. Within the overarching goal that the value of software, and its vital role in the production of research results, will be accepted across all levels of the research sector (e.g., international initiatives and national governments, through to universities and national laboratories), the following focus areas are important (which includes ideas from [RSE in 2030](#)):

People

1. Support for social infrastructures that support communities such as national and regional RSE associations, and thematic communities (e.g., training), particularly in the Global South.

2. Recognition and reward of research software work in all research performing positions, and national research assessment activities. This includes increased awareness of the RSE career, supported by a more standardised career path.
3. Focus on increasing belonging and broadening representation in the research software community.

Policy

1. Consideration within open science policies that include open software in their definition of how to implement support for research software (including resourcing).
2. Alignment of policies that support research software by stakeholders such as publishers (to support FAIRness and software citation), funders (to support FAIRness) and employers (to support career paths).
3. Stakeholder funding increasingly supports research software and its personnel (particularly with regard to software maintenance), and is provided by a range of stakeholders at different levels (from national governments and philanthropic funders through to research performing organisations whose staff develop research software assets).

Infrastructure

1. Maturation of tools that measure software, its community, and its impact, enabling rewards and recognition, and that assess compliance with standards and guidelines, such that they meet the needs of a range of stakeholders and are easily accessible.
2. Identification of needed infrastructure, including software repositories and registries, to enable support that provides sustainability.
3. Development and implementation of community-agreed standards in relevant areas.

As the ReSA mission is to enable collaborations with decision makers and key influencers, exactly what is focused on and why is up to the community.

3. ReSA's strategic direction

ReSA's role and niche in the scholarly landscape is to increase sustainability and resilience by fostering an international research software community that can adapt to the evolving needs of research stakeholders worldwide. There is a significant need for this work, and there are major challenges to enabling this internationally.

3.1 The critical need for ReSA

ReSA plays a critical part in this ecosystem by facilitating cohesion across national boundaries, stakeholder types, research disciplines, and thematic efforts; and within the broader research and open source software communities. Only ReSA fills this much needed niche, providing the social infrastructure that creates and upholds spaces to come together for key stakeholders across the entire research software community (though there are others that focus on specific parts). ReSA plays a critical role in facilitating the collaborations needed to enable the community to function globally in an open, accessible, and inclusive manner, contributing to the evolution of a research ecosystem that supports research software and its personnel. ReSA connects diverse knowledge communities with resources, power, and each other.

The depth of sectoral support for ReSA illustrates the demand for this expertise, and can be seen through the range of key influencers and decision makers engaged with ReSA. ReSA's supporters include [Founding Members](#); [Organisational Members](#); and [current and previous sponsors](#). ReSA's supporters actively contribute to advancing the development, recognition, and sustainability of research software, which in turn drives progress in the global research community. The 24 Founding and Organisational Member are comprised of the following organisations:

The demand for the opportunities that ReSA offers can be seen through the increasing number of community conversations that see value in becoming ReSA task forces. [ReSA task forces](#) are community-led initiatives to create international solutions that can also be used to solve challenges in local environments. These task forces rely on participants contributing their time to collaborate to solve community problems. [Support for task forces](#) is provided by community members in some cases, such as philanthropic funding for the [FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\) Working Group](#) jointly convened by ReSA, Research Data Alliance (RDA) and FORCE11, which developed the [FAIR4RS Principles](#); and RDA [Tiger](#) financial support for the joint ReSA-RDA [Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software \(PRO4RS\) Working Group](#).

It is important to clarify that ReSA seeks to work through existing organisations and communities. ReSA facilitates conversations between leaders, decision makers, and influencers, with the aim that these then engage their own communities on relevant topics. Consequently, ReSA generally focuses on research software communities that have reached sufficient maturity for high-level stakeholders to be present. In some cases these conversations may also identify gaps in areas that ReSA forums or task

forces could address, such as communities where research software is less recognised.

ReSA also focuses on areas where collaborations are needed. In some parts of the research software sector there already exist very valuable initiatives to engage multiple stakeholders, and ReSA does not generally attempt to engage in these areas where cross-organisational conversations are already flourishing. For example, ReSA does not focus on the content of software development, which can be considered [one of the four pillars of RSE](#), in addition to people, policy, and infrastructure. This area is already relatively well-served by initiatives such as the international RSE movement, which plays an important role in the sector with its primary focus on RSEs themselves and the needs of the RSE community.

Whilst ReSA facilitates collaborations that address many issues significant to the RSE movement, ReSA does not start from the specific viewpoint of RSEs, but from all parts of the research software community, including funders, publishers, infrastructure providers, etc. The [International Council of RSE Associations](#) and the [national and regional RSE associations](#) are only some of the stakeholders that ReSA engages. Ultimately ReSA and the RSE movement may address some of the same challenges (as RSEs do engage with the leaders and decision makers in organisations or initiatives that ReSA has as its primary audience); however, ReSA and the RSE movement have different starting points and utilise different approaches to achieve this.

3.2 ReSA's theory of change

ReSA is supported by a range of stakeholders to function as a backbone organisation across the research sector to increase the community's ability to collectively impact achievement of the shared vision that research software is recognised and valued as a fundamental and vital component of research worldwide. Backbone organisations enable collaboration in a coordinated effort across multiple stakeholders to achieve a common goal. ReSA supports collective impact by providing the social infrastructure needed to foster the cross-organisational

communication, alignment, and collaboration required to achieve sectoral change. ReSA's mission is to provide this for the research sector.

ReSA's theory of change describes how ReSA's inputs and activities lead to the achievement of desired outcomes and impacts. ReSA theory of change (or impact framework) has three pillars of change, as shown in the following figure. The categories of activities for the three pillars (of exchange, engage, and evolve) also form the basis of the [ReSA engagement plan](#).

Examples of ReSA's function for each of the three pillars is as follows.

Pillar 1: Exchange

- ReSA facilitates exchange of information to increase knowledge flow in the community. ReSA supports information flow by sharing information (e.g., monthly newsletter, social media posts), analysing relevant issues, and developing [resources](#) that support the recognition and valuing of research software as a key component of research. Community members are encouraged to contribute information to support this knowledge exchange.

Pillar 2: Engage

- ReSA acts as a coordinating body between national/regional, disciplinary, or thematically-focused organisations that are working on related tasks. ReSA's forums (e.g., [Research Software Funders Forum](#), [Research Software Infrastructure Forum](#)) and [task forces](#)) aim to bring together particular groupings of stakeholders to identify and focus on challenges and solutions for a particular area, at the international level.

Pillar 3: Evolve

- ReSA evolves leadership of a global community of research software champions and supporters with diverse perspectives through its engagement with the ReSA [Steering Committee](#), [Founding Members](#), and [Organisational Members](#). These have been responsible for outcomes such as the [Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability \(ADORE.software\)](#).

3.3 ReSA's achievements and challenges

ReSA's success is also demonstrated through its ability to engage the research community to achieve sector-wide impacts, which include:

1. [Funders](#) (e.g., government, industry): Leadership of a [research software funders community](#) that has engaged 60+ funding organisations in its goal to address common challenges and better coordinate investment globally, including development of the [Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability \(ADORE.software\)](#).
2. [Policy makers](#) (e.g., government, publishers, infrastructure providers, research organisations): Engaging in the drafting of key international policy documents from [UNESCO](#) and [OECD](#), which has led to the inclusion and recognition of research software as a crucial part of open science.

3. RSE associations (e.g., regional, national): Supporting the RSE community as secretariat for the [International Council of RSE Associations](#); compiling a list of [resources on how to create an RSE group \(within an organisation\) or association \(national, etc\)](#); and contributing to [RSE research](#).
4. Research software infrastructure providers (e.g., for profit and not for profit): Co-chairing the [Research Software Infrastructure Forum](#) to consider how to collectively address common challenges.
5. University consortia: Facilitating [Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software \(PRO4RS\)](#), a joint ReSA and [RDA](#) working group to help build our collection of [institutional policies](#) and consider how to better share these with interested stakeholders.
6. Publishers (e.g., for profit and not for profit): Supporting the ReSA task force on [code availability by publishers](#) to engage publishers in the coordination needed to gain wide-scale cultural change.
7. Thematic communities (e.g., training, citation): Co-leading the drafting of the [FAIR for Research Software Principles](#) (FAIR4RS) which engaged 500+ community members, with outcomes documented in a [two-year adoption update](#); and supporting ReSA [task forces](#) on [Actionable Guidelines for Making Research Software FAIR](#), and [FAIR4RS Review](#) that aims to understand where the principles have and have not been adopted, and why.
8. Research on research software (metascience): Co-authoring a [position paper](#) on the criticality of research software in AI-driven research.

However, there is still more work to be done to ensure that ReSA engages comprehensively with its key stakeholders, to catalyse conversations in more areas where increased community collaboration would be beneficial.

This 2025–2028 strategic plan recognises some maturation of the international research sector to now incorporate research software in high-level discussions since the [previous ReSA strategic plan](#) (2021–2023), such as the inclusion of open software in the [UNESCO](#) definition of open science. However, many needs remain to increase recognition and support for research software beyond strategic rhetoric, and in achievement of this level of recognition uniformly across the globe.

ReSA also faces challenges in terms of:

1. Engaging the breadth of the research software community (in terms of both types of stakeholders and geographics areas) with limited resources.
2. Enabling increased representation of the community in broader research sector discussions, where more research software champions are needed in a wide variety of conversations.
3. Demonstrating ReSA’s impact, which is a common issue for social infrastructures.
4. Identifying resourcing, as some stakeholders (such as national governments) face challenges in contributing to financial international efforts; and many organisations need time to build in-kind support into strategic aims.
5. Continuing to clarify the difference between ReSA and the RSE movement, to maximise opportunities for each to leverage the other.

4. ReSA initiatives 2025–2028

There are a number of areas where ReSA will focus its activities in 2025–2028, in response to the preceding analysis. The framing of these draws on delineations of how backbone organisations like ReSA can increase community mobilisation for success. ReSA utilises the Tamarack Institute’s [phases of collective impact](#) and Educopia’s [community cultivation framework lifecycle](#) to support its strategic planning. The following sections include details of proposed projects for 2025–2028.

Additional resourcing is needed to enable many of these activities to occur.

The goals are classified as an ongoing or stage 1, 2, or 3 activity. The three stages are used to show the progression of an activity. In some cases commencement of each stage of activities may loosely align a one year period, but not necessarily.

To support achievement of its strategic goals, a primary goal of ReSA's operations in 2025–28 is to undertake fundraising to achieve the above goals. ReSA seeks partners who are interested in joining a [dynamic group of organisations](#) that are coordinating across government organisations and global communities to accelerate research. ReSA's [2024 budget](#) of USD\$318,000 supports minimal operations through 1.5 full-time equivalent staff (spread across three people), travel, and fiscal sponsorship fees. ReSA aims to extend its sustainable operational base to support at least three full-time staff; a Director, Program Manager, and Community and Communications Manager. In the future this could expand to additional roles such as a Policy and Campaigns Officer and a Membership Manager.

4.1 Pillar 1: Exchange information to increase knowledge flow in community

Ongoing activity:

- Co-author of [position papers, responses to requests for information, blogs](#), etc., that provide the community with baseline data, identification of key issues and gaps, progress on initiatives, etc.
- Provide community resources including databases of [research software funding](#) and [policies that support research software for research organisations](#),
- Promotion of [Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability](#). (ADORE.software) and updating of the ADORE.software [toolkit](#) that supports implementation.
- Release a monthly [newsletter](#) that identifies and promotes news and resources, such as international recommendations, emerging best practice, impact metrics, and national strategies.
- Use social media to broaden audience engagement.

- Share information at ReSA forums to share targeted information to those stakeholders.

Stage 1/2/3 activity:

- Identify priority areas where additional baseline data and analysis is needed to support recognition of research software and its personnel, and co-lead projects to fulfill these needs (ideally through a forum or task force with this focus).

Stage 1/2/3 activity:

- Scope the viability of establishment of other resources needed to support valuing of research software internationally, such as journal special issues (or a new journal if needed), and an international research software and personnel awards program.
- Implement recommendations of this scoping exercise.

4.2 Pillar 2: Engage community collaborations to solve common issues

Ongoing activity:

1. Convene forums: [Research Software Funders Forum](#), [Research Software Infrastructure Forum](#), [International Council of RSE Associations](#), [ADORE.software Secretariat](#), and one new forum.
2. Facilitate [task forces](#) that enable parts of the community to address shared local challenges that will benefit from global solutions.

Stage 1/2/3 activity: Create additional [forums](#) that enable new groupings of stakeholders to identify the community-wide issues that would benefit from increased collaboration. Possible stakeholder groups and/or areas include publishers, policymakers, skills and training, research performing organisations, impact evaluation, university consortia, and research on research software initiatives.

Stage 1/2/3 activity: Facilitate additional task forces on priority areas arising from forums and other initiatives. Task forces are proposed and led by community members, with ReSA serving as a coordinating body between national/regional organisations, disciplinary, and/or thematically focused organisations that are working on related tasks. Task forces may enable activities or create resources such as standards, white papers, best practice exemplars, etc.

Stage 1 activity:

- Support forums to create task forces (e.g., the Funders Forum convened four working groups in 2022-2023).

Stage 1 activity:

- Form committees led by ReSA to commence implementation of the outcomes of the 2024 scoping report, [Towards an international research software conference](#) to work towards outcomes such as a new international conference, and/or workshops at existing events, and/or champions program.
- Convene a hybrid, annual, international research software community conference that engages key stakeholders within the research software community to improve collaboration and coordination (ideally commencing in 2026).

4.3 Pillar 3: Evolve governance of a global community to achieve shared vision

Stage 1 activity:

- Convene the Community Leaders Forum to bring together a representative group of research software leaders, decision makers, and influencers, to function as a community body with a shared vision, making decisions about the community's priorities and plans. ReSA governance, organisational membership, and forums could provide some pathways into this (with representatives from each comprising some of the Community Leaders Forum), with other stakeholder groups becoming represented through

additional forums. Consideration is also needed of how to engage voices not represented by an existing organisation or community.

Stage 2/3 activity:

- Continue to convene the Community Leaders Forum to identify shared vision and begin to function as a body that can identify community priorities (and ultimately assist in coordination to address these). The Forum could aim to create longer-term outcomes such as development of a decadal plan for research software, as an equivalent to research data plans such as the International Science Council (ISC) Committee on Data (CODATA)'s [Decadal Programme: Making Data Work for Cross-Domain Grand Challenges](#).

5. Risk management

Risk	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation strategy
Challenges in gaining resourcing, including recruiting organisational members	Medium	High	Strategic approach to investor engagement. Utilise Steering Committee networks
Limited resources to manage existing and planned projects	High	High	Stage development to match resourcing
Staff retention	Medium	Medium	Be transparent on funding situation, improve documentation to capture ReSA plans and processes

Ability of Steering Committee to contribute to ReSA development	Low	Medium	Set realistic expectations and establish off-boarding strategy
Difficulty in demonstrating ReSA's value	Medium	High	Utilise strategic and engagement plans to focus activities and measure impact
Difficulty in demonstrating ReSA's niche, especially due to the perceived or real overlap with RSE movement	Medium	High	Utilise strategic and engagement plans to delineate different stakeholder focus and approach